

To Study the Problems Faced by The Respondents in Adoption of Swachh Bharat Mission Facilities

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Abstract

"Sanitation is more important than independence".

Mahatma Gandhi

India covered with 17.5 per cent of the world population. The condition of, hygiene and sanitation, facility of drinking water was very gigantic since large decades. The irrelevant behavior in order to address this challenge was responsible for the many risks were faced by respondents, found that the majority of respondents 80.00% were faced a problem of lack of dustbins, followed by 69.00% respondents were faced a problem of lack of facilities in toilet like water, light and 67.00% respondents stated the officer asked for bribe to get toilet constructed, 63.00% respondents, lack of proper knowledge and information about Swachh Bharat Mission.

Keywords

Sanitation, Drinking Water, Hygiene and Respondents.

Introduction

Cleanliness and sanitation were an integral part of Gandhian way of living. His dream was total sanitation for all. He used to emphasize that cleanliness is the most important for physical wellbeing and a healthy environment.

India is the 7th largest country in the world and 2nd most crowded nation in the world. As per census report 2011, the population of India comprised 1.21 billion. The literacy rate of country 74.04 percent, 82.14 percent for male literacy and 65.46 per cent for female literacy only. Suitable reasons behind the rapidly growing India's population are poor financial condition of the people, lack of proper education, and increased level of birth rate etc. Nearly 30 per cent population of India affected by poverty. It was found in the report of United Nation Development Program in 2014. that multidimensional Poverty Index showed 56 per cent people in India had poor status in thesectionofeducation, health, sanitation and standards of living indicators. Poor the sanitation continues to have a significant impact on the country. Thereport of united nationrevealed that, 55 per cent people in Indiawere defecating in theopen. Defecationin open causes spreading many diseases through insect moving from one place to another.

The 1981 Census revealed rural sanitation coverage was only around 1percent. The lack of sanitation had been a leading cause of diarrhea among children (under five year) resulting in stunting among children and also resulted in several preventable child deaths. Sanitation is also a critical aspect for ensuring safety and dignity for women. In 1986 a programme Central Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP) which solely focused on sanitation was introduced. The first nationwide centrally sponsored programme aimed to provide safe sanitation in rural areas. Since the programme did not address the question of Open Defecation, it did not provide desired results. **source :Ahuja (2019)**

In 1999, Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC)with a vision to eradicate open defecation by 2017 was launched. This was followed by the launch of Nirmal Gram Puraskar, SampurnaSwachataAndolana Scheme and other initiatives to strengthen the TSC. In 2006, TSC was merged with IndiraAwasYojana (IAY), then a flagship scheme under the

Ministry of Rural Development which addressed rural housing needs by giving financial assistance for the construction of dwelling units for Below Poverty Line (BPL) families. The convergence allowed the use of funds for the construction of sanitary toilets in IAY houses. Toilets were constructed in large numbers, but the quality of construction remained a concern and there was no focus on changing behavior at the ground level in promotion of usage of toilets. Many households who had started using toilets slipped back to defecating in the open.

According to the census of 2011, 53.1 per cent (63.6 per cent in 2001) of the households in India do not have a toilet, with the percentage being as high as 69.3 per cent (78.1 per cent in 2001) in rural areas and 18.6 per cent (26.3 per cent in 2001) in urban areas. These facts have also been reconfirmed by another report released on 6th March 2012 by the WHO/UNICEF's Joint Monitoring Programme on sanitation for the Millennium Development Goals, which has also indicated that 59 per cent (626 million) Indians still do not have access to toilets and practice open defecation and that majority of them live in rural areas. **Source : Mathur (2019)**

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study the problems faced by the respondents in adoption of Swachh Bharat Mission facilities.

Review of Literature

The related review of the study are following:

"The Final Frontier" Report (2014) published in The Economist newspaper states that the problem of open defecation in India cannot be resolved for decades yet, through the mere availability of government-built latrines. The report further highlights that the media, along with the schools, needs to play a crucial role in spreading awareness about the health and economic benefits of using toilets and maintaining hygiene.

Sangita Vyas (2014) the results of the SQUAT survey corroborate this interpretation. In the survey, less than 1% of men and only 5% of women who defecate in the open suggest that lack of access to water could be a reason not to use a latrine. In our related qualitative research project, which we have conducted on sanitation preferences and beliefs in rural India and Nepal, water was rarely raised as a constraint on latrine use in 99 in-depth semi-structured interviews.

Anjana Kuberan, et al. (2015) found that 45 per cent of the participants were not following any methods of water treatment and among them half of the participants felt that water available to them was clean and did not require any additional treatment. 25 per cent of the participants surveyed did not have access to toilets inside their household leaving them with the options of using community toilets, open defecation or sharing the toilets with other households which in turn promotes the increase in incidence of water-borne disease.

Rao and Subbarao (2015) studied the issues and concerns of Swachh Bharat Ahiyan. The study also focused on Gandhian concept of sanitation. The study concluded that it is the opportunity and responsibility of the citizens, media, social media, civil society, organizations, professionals, youths, students, and teachers to declare their ownership of the campaign by simply reporting the instances of manual scavenging.

Anuj Mittal et al. (2016) revealed the 70% population lack toilet in their houses because 40% of them had no money to build toilet, whereas 28% wanted to go out of the houses for defecation. According to recent survey conducted to Indian Government, 49% follow open air defecation and rest use toilets. The situation needs to be addressed as high priority and it also shows that a deeper penetration by Government agencies should be done to reach every household.

MP Sheethal, SK Shashikantha (2016) revealed the majority of the study subjects without latrine, and 18% practiced open air defecation. Among the subjects who practiced open air defecation, 37 (80.4%) of them were aware of the financial assistance and the most common reasons for not obtaining financial benefits were lack of space (22%), delayed sanction of money (19%), comfortable with open air defecation (11%), no own house (9%), lack of water supply (9%) and the rest had applied for the financial assistance.

Snehlata Singh (2018) observed that people clean their homes and shops and throw the garbage on the street without considering its implications. It is evident that even students of elite schools throw garbage on the ground even in the presence of garbage bins. Keeping our community clean and well-kept can sometimes feel like fighting a losing battle. This shows our attitude towards cleanliness and hygiene. Another habit that is commonly found in our society is spitting openly. People spit paan/gutka from running

vehicles without considering the pedestrians walking on the road. This practice not only affects the environment but is also an eyesore. Another area that needs consideration is the horrible condition of public toilets. The shortage of public toilets is a big challenge; hence people are compelled to use open spaces to answer the call of nature. The toilets that do exist are in such pathetic condition that one cannot use them. It should be our basic sense of responsibility to keep our community clean. Anti-litter campaigns should be held to create awareness among the general public and motivate them to take up the broom.

Main Text

Need For Swachh Bharat Mission

Sanitation is the basic need of human beings. Safe sanitation is not a borrowed modern concept from the west rather there are historical evidences in India's ancient civilization (Sindhu valley) regarding scientific methods used in toilets construction and waste management. But hundreds of years of servility took away the important value of Swachhata from India's social system. Despite the widely accepted fact related to critical importance of sanitation and personal hygiene, the sanitation coverage of India was as low as 39 per cent till 2014. This was severely affecting health and dignity of people in rural areas, especially of women and children.

In 2012, the Central Government launched Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA), with an aim to provide 100 percent access to toilets in rural households by 2022. NBA was launched in convergence with Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). NBA was an update of TSC with renewed strategies and modified guidelines and objectives to accelerate sanitation coverage in the rural areas. An inefficient solid and liquid waste management system create serious negative environmental impacts like infectious diseases, land and water pollution, obstruction of drains and loss of biodiversity. Mane (2014) found in his study that 1000 children die daily in India from diarrhea, which was spreading due to defecating in open, unhygienic condition, and poor sanitation. Access to poor sanitation is not just unpleasant, it is dangerous, when people have no option but to defecate in the open, they run the risk of catching or spreading an infectious disease like diarrhea, cholera. Women and girls are particularly vulnerable when they do not have access to a private toilet. Beyond health risks, poor sanitation can have several negative impacts. It leaves women and girls open to the dangers of harassment and assault by men and attacks by animals (Geertz et al., 2018), (Saleem, Burdett, & Heaslip, 2019) (Sommer, Ferron, Cavill, & House, 2015). Anecdotal evidence and grey literature suggest that women reported feeling a sense of shame, helplessness and fear when defecating in the open. Women's rights were also checked, as they had to wait for defecation until night to protect their privacy.

There was a review conducted on rural sanitation for the evaluation of performance of the program in the last of "11th-5 Year plan, the Planning Commission of India. The findings revealed that the conditions of improper sanitation were improving slowly in many states. By keeping these all facts in the mind in order to accelerate the efforts to achieve universal sanitation coverage and to put focus on sanitation, the Prime Minister of India launched the Swachh Bharat Mission on 2nd October, 2014. The aim of SBM is to achieve Swachh Bharat by 2019, as a fitting tribute to Mahatma Gandhi on his 150th Birth Anniversary. The SBM has two Sub-Missions, the Swachh Bharat Mission (Gamin) and the Swachh Bharat Mission (Urban), Ministry of Drinking water and sanitation is the nodal body ministry for SBM(G) and Ministry of urban development is the nodal Ministry of SBM (U). The levels of cleanliness in rural areas can be achieved through Solid and Liquid Waste Management activities and making Gram Panchayats Open Defecation Free (ODF), clean and sanitized. It is India's biggest ever cleanliness drive and 3 million government employees and school and college students of India participated in this event. The core objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) are to bring about an improvement in the general quality of life in the rural areas, by promoting cleanliness, hygiene and eliminating open defecation and to accelerate sanitation coverage in rural areas to achieve the vision of Swachh Bharat by 2nd October 2019.

The main objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) are-

- i. To bring about an improvement in the general quality of life in the rural areas, by promoting cleanliness, hygiene and eliminating open defecation.
- ii. To accelerate sanitation coverage in rural areas to achieve the vision of Swachh Bharat by 2nd October 2019.
- iii. To motivate Communities and Panchayati Raj Institutions to adopt sustainable sanitation practices and facilities through awareness creation and health education.

iv. To encourage cost effective and appropriate technologies for ecologically safe and sustainable sanitation.

v. To develop where required, Community managed sanitation systems focusing on scientific Solid & Liquid Waste Management systems for overall cleanliness in the rural areas.

Components of SBM(G):-

Individual Household Latrines, Community Sanitary Complex and Solid and Liquid Waste Management are the important components of SBM (G). Institutional toilets like School toilets and Anganwadi toilets earlier implemented as part of TSC/NBA have been transferred to the Ministries in-charge of Department of School Education and Department of Women and Child Development, respectively.

Community Sanitary Complex

Community Sanitary Complexes comprising an appropriate number of toilet seats, bathing cubicles, washing platforms, Wash basins etc, can be set up in a place in the village acceptable and accessible to all. Ordinarily such Complexes shall be constructed only when there is lack of space in the village for construction of household toilets and the Community/GP owns up the responsibility of their operation and maintenance and gives a specific demand for the same. Such Complexes can be made at Public places, markets; bus stands etc., where large scale congregation of people takes place. The maximum support per unit prescribed for a Community Sanitary Complex is Rs.2 lakh. Sharing pattern amongst Central Government, State Government and the Community shall be in the ratio of 60:30:10. **source: Government of tamil nadu official website (2024).**

For Solid Waste Management:

States are to decide the technologies suitable to their areas. Technologies identified by the Committee on Technologies may also be considered for implementation. Collection, segregation and safe disposal of household garbage, decentralized systems like household composting and biogas plants shall be permitted. Activities related to maximum reuse of organic solid wastes as manure should be adopted. Such technologies may include vermi-composting, NADEP composting, or any other composting method, individual and community biogas plants. Funds allocated for Solid and Liquid Waste Management may be used to implement safe disposal solutions for menstrual waste (used sanitary cloths and pads) and setting up incinerators in Schools, Women's Community Sanitary Complexes, Primary Health Centre, or in any other suitable place in village and collection mechanisms etc can be taken up. Technologies may include appropriate options that are socially acceptable and environmentally safe.

For Liquid Waste Management:

States are to identify suitable technologies. Methods adopted for management of liquid wastes may focus on maximum reuse of such waste for agriculture purpose with least operation and maintenance costs. For collection of waste water, low-cost drainage/ small bore system, soakage pit may be adopted. For treatment of waste water, the following technologies may inter-alia be considered.

SBM-Phase 2nd referred ODF Plus

For ensuring that open defecation free behaviors are sustained and solid and liquid management facilities are accessible, the government has launched Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) phase II also referred as ODF plus in February, 2020. The programme would be implemented in a mission mode till 2024-25, with a total outlay of Rs. 1,40,881, crores. of this Rs 52,497 crore will be allocated from the budget of the Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation while the remaining amount will be allocated from the funds being released under 15th Finance Commission, MGNREGA and revenue generation models particularly for solid and liquid waste management. **Source: PIB (2020)** Under the program, provision for incentive of Rs.12000/- for construction of individual Household Toilet to the newly emerging eligible households as per the existing norms will continue. Funding norms for Solid and Liquid Waste Management (SLWM) have been rationalized and changed to per capita basis in place of no. of households. The financial assistance to the Gram Panchayats (GPs) for construction of Community Managed Sanitary Complex (CMSC) at village level has been increased from Rs. 2 lakh to Rs. 3 lakh per CMSC.

Swachh Bharat Mission in Uttar Pradesh

Out of all state of India, the population of Uttar Pradesh comprised 16.5 per cent of India in 2011 in which 22.27 per cent people have been living in urban regions while 77.33 per cent in rural area. Out of 22 million households, 27.6 per cent have water closet toilet, 4.2 per cent have pit toilet, 1.7 per cent have other toilet and 64.4 people have no toilet and they were practicing open defecation which was a major sanitation challenge in Uttar Pradesh.

Importance of the Study-

This study will be useful to the educationist, researchers, extension worker experiment institutions, private organization, self-help groups, non-government organization, medical sector, and those who are engaged in the work of health and sanitation for the betterment of rural India. Moreover, the study will be helpful for various mass media agencies, department, television, channels etc. who are engaged in broadcasting the information related to health and sanitation.

Methodology

Research methodology is the specific procedure or techniques that are used to clarify, select process and analyze information about a topic. It is the blue print of the research architect. In this chapter an attempt has made to critically evaluate and explain various methods and procedure followed under the present study. There were 75 district in Uttar Pradesh in which Baghpat district of western Uttar Pradesh was selected for study. Out of 6 blocks of Baghpat district two blocks Baghpat and Baraut were selected purposively. Out of these two blocks 2-2 villages from each block were selected and out of these 2-2 villages, 25-25 beneficiaries of S.B.M. were taken for the study. Hence, all together (25 respondents of 4 villages) 100 respondents were the total number of sample size. As far (11 independent variable like age, sex, caste, education etc.) and (3 dependent variable like knowledge, utilization/adoption, problems) concluded for bring out the outcomes under this study. Collection of data was done by personal structured interview schedule and official website of ministry of drinking water and sanitation and the collected data were examined by suitable statistics methods as per need to bring fruitful implications.

Research tools and techniques were applied

Keeping in view of the purpose of the study knowledge, function and work done under the S.B.M. project in rural area, and adoption of S.B.M. facilities by the respondent, the personal interview schedule technique was used for the collection of data. The semi structure interview schedule was constructed by investigator for data collection. The semi structure schedule tested on 20 respondents, after tested some modification for the decrement were done and prepare well developed schedule for the data collection.

A. Tabulation and classification:

Total data were classified in different group/categories and there after tabulated.

B. Frequency and percentage:

Frequency was calculated to find out the number of respondents in a particular category. The percentage value was calculated by dividing the frequency of a particular cell by total number of respondents in particular category and multiplying by 100.

$$\text{Percentage} = (\text{Value} / \text{Total value}) \times 100$$

or

$$P (\%) = n \times 100 / N$$

Where,

P= percentage

n = frequency of particular cell

N = total number of respondents in the particular category

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Problems of respondents in adoption of Swacch Bharat Mission facilities

S. No.	Problems	Agree	Disagree
1	Difficulty in changing of mind set to use the toilet & latrine?	34 (34.00%)	66 (66.00%)
2	Due to problem for cleaning and maintenance of the toilet and latrine?	38 (38.00%)	62 (62.00%)
3	Delay in release of fund from concerned Officials.	30 (30.00%)	70 (70.00%)
4	Allocate fund under the S.B.M.is not sufficient for toilet construction work.	60 (60.00%)	40 (40.00%)
5	Officer asked for bribe to get toilet constructed.	67 (67.00%)	33 (33.00%)
6	Lack of facilities in toilet & latrine like, water and light.	69 (69.00%)	31 (31.00%)
7	Lack of proper knowledge and information about S.B.M.	63 (63.00%)	37 (37.00%)
8	Less involvement, co-operation and dedication of Panchayati raj institution (PRI) members.	62 (62.00%)	38 (38.00%)

9	Lack of infrastructure for garbage management in village.	43 (43.00%)	47 (47.00%)
10	Lack of dustbins in village.	80 (80.00%)	20 (20.00%)

Conclusion

Table 1: revealed that the majority of respondents 80.00% were faced problem of lack of dustbins in village followed by 69.00% respondents were faced a problem of lack of facilities in toilet like water, light and 67.00% stated that the officer asked for bribe to get toilet constructed, 63.00% respondents were faced problem of lack of information about S.B.M. facilities, 62.00% were stated that less involvement, cooperation and dedication of Panchayati raj institution (PRI) members, 60.00% were stated that the allocated fund under the S.B.M. is not sufficient for toilet construction, 43.00% were faced problem lack of infrastructure for garbage management, 38.00% respondents were have a problem for cleaning and maintenance of toilet and problem of 34.00% respondents changing in mind set to use the toilet, 30.00% were stated that delay in release of fund from concerned officials.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Most of the respondents were having problem of unavailability of dustbins in their villages. They were requesting to install the dustbins at major locations in village so they can access it conveniently and dispose the waste properly.
2. The villages were facing problem of smaller number of sweepers to clean the drains, streets and public places of village. As the number was less, the more stress was seen on available workers and irregularities in cleanliness had seen in village. The villagers were requesting to increase the number of workers to bring proper management of sanitation in village.
3. In the study, it was also found that some of the respondents don't have toilet facility, so they still defecating in open. For eliminating this situation the community toilets and public toilets might be the best possible solution for those who are defecating in open.
4. Government should take local effort to implement the programme. The involvement of local bodies to design and execute the SBM is important. Government should involve local bodies, local people and local Non-government organizations in SBM for widen the programme.
5. It was found that many of the respondents do not aware about S.B.M. facilities and its components. Awareness programmes must be started.
6. There were several constraints faced by beneficiaries as well as in which major one was, officer asked for bribe to get toilet constructed. Government should take action against those officers who take bribe.
7. The local bodies of selected area and the selected beneficiaries suggested the fund allocated by the government under the S.B.M. is not sufficient for toilet construction. Sufficient fund must be allocated for toilet construction.

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